

THE INFLUENCE OF PUBLIC POLICY TRANSPARENCY ON CITIZENS PARTICIPATION AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN MEDAN: A COMPREHENSIVE SEM-PLS ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the extent to which the innovation variable of the E-Government application affects the increase in public trust and increase community involvement through the effectiveness of E-Government as an intervening variable. The subject of this study is the community/residents of Medan City, where the variables in this study are independent variables, namely E-Government application innovation, dependent variables, namely variables of increasing public trust and increasing community involvement and intervening variables are variables of E-Government effectiveness. The results of data analysis were carried out by SEM analysis using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The data collection technique is by observation and documentation studies. The research method uses a quantitative descriptive method of data analysis using *the structural equation model* (SEM) method, where the results of data processing using the SEM method are carried out with the PLS 4.0 application. Based on the results of the study, the variable of public policy transparency partially affects community involvement, creates accountability and affects public policy innovation. The variable of public policy innovation affects community involvement and creates accountability. Simultaneously, public policy transparency affects community involvement and has the effect of creating accountability through public policy innovation variables as intervening variables. The more transparent public policies are accompanied by community involvement and creating accountability to be open, it will have an impact on the process of creating innovations in public policies intended to create policies that are in favor of the community.

Keywords: E-Government Effectiveness, E-Government Application Innovation, Increasing Public Trust, Increasing Community Involvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Public policy is one of the policies that needs to be carried out in order to create a service program by listening to complaints and suggestions from the community, where this public policy is a policy made that is based on criticism, suggestions and input from the community (Gamerding, Alexander, Just, Sine N. and Lantz, 2023). Public policies must be felt by the community, not only by a person and a group of people, where the community is required to provide input and suggestions to complement public policies that will be made for the benefit of the community (Sapat et al., 2022).

Every public policy that wants to be triggered and wants to be programmed requires a clear pattern and must listen to the complaints of the community, where the public policy pattern is an approach or methodology used by the government to design, implement, and evaluate policies that aim to solve public problems or achieve certain goals in society (Simonofski, Anthony, 2021). Public policy patterns can be influenced by a variety of factors, including political, economic, social, cultural, and technological. Community participation, transparency, and accountability also play an important role in the successful implementation of public policies (Aysolmaz, Banu, Müller & and Meacham, 2023).

The implementation of public policy is supported by the will of the leadership, where leadership plays an important role in creating good innovations for the implementation of a policy, where a good policy must be a policy that is in favor of the community and does not always harm the community (Marent, Benjamin, Henwood & and Darking, 2023). In implementing public policy, the Government must first find and define problems that require government intervention, where these problems must be solved through policies implemented through the making of Undnag-Law, Government Regulations and also Regional Regulations (Ly, Bora and Ly, 2023).

After finding a problem, then the Government will determine priorities and decide which problems will be handled. This is done so that existing public policies do not overlap which causes confusion among government officials, so that the Government must absorb the aspirations of the community in order to determine policies that must be prioritized first (Sefa-Nyarko, Clement, Okafor-Yarwood, Ifesinachi and Boadu, 2021) The determination of the formulation of public policies requires a process of transparency and accountability, where transparency is needed so that later in the formulation of problems in laws, government regulations and also regional regulations do not harm the community. This transparency process must be truly implemented, input from the community must be adopted and coordinated into the formulation of public policies that want to be implemented (Kolcava, Dennis, Rudolph & and Bernauer, 2021).

The existing transparency of public policies can be seen from the emergence of information related to public policies that must be easily accessible to the public. It includes information about how policies are formulated, who is involved, the data used, and the decisions taken. This is necessary so that later the resulting policies tend to be accepted by the public, and can create certainty so that the policy does not harm the community (Ruppen, Désirée and Brugger, 2022).

The government must provide a clear and complete report on policy implementation, including the budget used, the results achieved, and the challenges faced. This clear and complete report is part of accountability, where reports on public policies related to the benefit of the community must be accountable, where this accountability process will result in transparency or information disclosure, where the public can obtain the information by accessing information through the website of a State institution that discusses public policies in the Peemrintahan Institute (Grants, Dorothy, 2023).

In making public policies, the Government must be ready to be supervised by the public, where the process of monitoring and evaluating policies must be open to the public. The results of the evaluation must be published and accessible to the public, where the community must really carefully follow every step that is an aspiration to the Government so that this public policy is not hindered, and can even be carried out properly by the government (Tejedo-Romero, Francisca, 2022).

The government must make the policies that are made create solutions that really solve problems, where existing policies require innovations that are able to find various solutions to existing problems that are really needed by the community in order to create policies that are really needed by the community (Huang, Gillan Chi Lun and Chen, 2021). With good innovation, it will make it easier for the Government to get alternatives from various existing conclusions in the form of solutions to each problem, where alternative solutions are needed so that later existing policies can be implemented and always prioritize the interests of the community (Dashwood et al.,

2022). This public policy requires significant community involvement. This is done so that later the public can find out whether the policies that will be produced are in accordance with the community's expectations or not, as well as whether the existing policies can be implemented properly or not, so that the policies are on target and can be accounted for in a transparent, accountable, and accountable manner that prioritizes the welfare of the community (Myodayeva, 2021).

Public officials must act with integrity and honesty, avoid conflicts of interest, and ensure that all their actions can be accounted for, transparent and transparent, where the Government's attitude and actions must reflect creating policies that are in favor of the people, where the people are the main factor in the process of creating policies that stem from the root problems in society (Archidis, Jean, 2021).

Medan has a population of 2,494,512 people, where the population cannot reach public policies from the Government, especially the Medina Regional Government. This is due to the lack of transparency of policymakers, which has an impact on the lack of community participation, as well as the lack of accountability that makes the policies of the Medan City Government not in accordance with the expectations of the community and not in accordance with the wishes of the community, thus harming the community.

Problem Formulation

The formulation of the problem that emerged from this study is how the variable of public policy transparency affects community involvement and creates accountability through public policy innovation as an intervening variable.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the extent to which the variable of public policy transparency affects community involvement and creates accountability through public policy innovation as an intervening variable.

Originality of Research

The subject of this study is the community/residents of Medan City, where the variables in this study are independent variables, namely public policy transparency, dependent variables, namely variables that increase community involvement and create accountability and intervening variables are public policy innovation variables. The results of data analysis were carried out by SEM analysis using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The data collection technique is by observation and documentation studies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Policy Transparency

Public policy transparency is a principle that requires the process of making, implementing, and evaluating policies to be carried out openly and accessible to the public. This transparency aims to ensure accountability, increase public trust, and encourage active participation of the public in the government process (Horváth, László, 2023). Transparency in public policy is the principle and practice of ensuring that the process of policy making, implementation, and evaluation is carried out openly and accessible to the public. This transparency is important to build public trust in the government and increase accountability (Mansoor, 2021).

The indicators of public policy transparency are:

1. Access to open information
2. Public participation in public policy
3. Data disclosure
4. Disclosure of information (Cortés-Cediel, María E., 2023)

Public Policy Innovation

Public policy innovation is an effort to create, develop, and implement new ideas in the policy-making process to increase the effectiveness, efficiency, and responsiveness of policies to the needs of the community (Ardanaz, Martin, Otálvaro-Ramírez, Susana and Scartascini, 2023). Innovation in public policy is key to answering modern challenges and improving people's welfare. By continuing to develop and implement new ideas, the government can become more adaptive, responsive, and effective in serving the community (Ogbe, 2022). Indicators of public policy innovation are:

1. Creativity and new ideas
2. Efficiency and effectiveness
3. Community engagement participation
4. Transparent use of data (Suebvises, 2019)

Community Involvement

Community involvement in public policy is the process by which citizens are actively involved in the decision-making, planning, implementation, and evaluation of policies that affect their lives (Matheus, Ricardo, Janssen, Marijn and Maheshwari, 2020). This involvement is important to ensure that the resulting policies are relevant, effective, and acceptable to the community (Falanga & Ferrão, 2021). Community engagement indicators are:

1. Community participation
2. Transparency and accountability
3. Community empowerment (Lourenço, 2023)

Creating Accountability

Creating accountability in public policy is an effort to ensure that policymakers, public officials, and government institutions are accountable for their actions and decisions (Brunswicker, Sabine, Pujol Priego, Laia and Almirall, 2019). Accountability is essential to increase public trust, reduce corruption, and ensure that public policies are executed efficiently and effectively (Guillard, Séverin and McGillivray, 2022). The indicators of creating quality are:

1. Transparency of information access
2. Supervision and evaluation
3. Public participation and responsiveness
4. Law enforcement and ethics (Guggisberg et al., 2022)

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the research is:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

1. Public policy transparency affects community involvement in Medan City
2. Public policy transparency has an effect on creating accountability
3. Public policy transparency affects public policy innovation
4. Public policy innovations affect community involvement in Medan City
5. Public policy innovation has an effect on creating accountability
6. Public policy transparency affects community involvement in Medan City through public policy innovation as an intervening variable
7. Public policy transparency has an effect on creating accountability through public policy innovation as an intervening variable

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This research method was carried out using a quantitative descriptive method using method analysis *Structural Equation Model* (SEM), where according to (Lim, Seng Boon, 2021) SEM analysis is a data analysis method aimed at finding out how the existing variables affect each other significantly. The population in this study is 2,494,512 residents of Medan City in 2023, where the sampling method is carried out using the *Simple random sampling*, which according to (Lim, Seng Boon, 2021) sampling method using *Simple random sampling* is a sampling in which the population is taken randomly and the samples taken cannot get the same opportunity when repeatedly taken.

The number of samples taken can be done using the slovin formula as follows:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2) = 2,494,512 / (1 + 2,494,512 \times 0.1^2) = 99.99 = 100 \text{ inhabitants of Medan City}$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results

The output of the SEM test can be described through the following *Bootstrapping* diagram:

Figure 2: *Bootstrapping Diagram*

Convergent Validity Analysis

(Lim, Seng Boon, 2021) states that the analysis *convergent validity* is one of the analyses that states that the data of the construct variables has led to validity. The test results *convergent validity* in this study, it is as follows:

Table 1: *Convergent Validity Test*

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Public Policy Transparency (X)	Crime Scene 1	0,851
	Crime Scene 2	0,871
	Crime Scene 3	0,862
	Crime Scene 4	0,812
Community Engagement (Y1)	KM 1	0,862
	KM 2	0,873
	KM 3	0,874
Creating Accountability (Y2)	MA 1	0,849
	MA 2	0,834
	MA 3	0,873
	MA 4	0,861
Public Policy Innovation (Z)	IKP 1	0,880
	IKP 2	0,764
	IKP 3	0,826
	IKP 4	0,865

Source: Results of Data Processing with PLS 3.0, 2024

The table above states that the data of each construct variable creates a significant data validity.

Analysis of Average Variant Extracted (AVE)

(Lim, Seng Boon, 2021) stated that the AVE test is one of the tests aimed at finding out whether or not the existing construction variable data is appropriate. The test results *Average Variant Extracted (AVE)* is in the following table:

Table 2: AVE Test

Variable	AVE
Public Policy Transparency (X)	0,833
Community Engagement (Y1)	0,873
Creating Accountability (Y2)	0,853
Public Policy Innovation (Z)	0,854

Source: Data Processing Results with PLS 4.0, 2024

The table above describes the *Average Variant Extracted (AVE)* value greater than 0.5 which means that the distribution of the existing variable data is appropriate and valid.

Composite Reliability Analysis

According to (Lim, Seng Boon, 2021) Testing *Composite Reliability* is an analysis to explain whether the existing data is relevant to be used for further data processing. This can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Composite Reliability Test

Variable	Composite Reliability
Public Policy Transparency (X)	0,881
Community Engagement (Y1)	0,821
Creating Accountability (Y2)	0,871
Public Policy Innovation (Z)	0,850

Source: Data Processing Results with PLS 4.0, 2024

The table above states that *the composite reliability* value is greater than 0.6, where the existing data is relevant and reliable.

Discriminant Validity Analysis

In confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) or structural equation modeling (SEM), the analysis of discriminatory validity is how much the relationship between construct variables affects each other. The results of *the Discriminant Validity* analysis can be seen in the following Table 5:

Table 5: Discriminant Validity Analysis

	Creating Accountability Moderating Effect 1	Creating Community Accountability Effect 2	Creating Accountability Moderating Effect 3	Creating Accountability Moderating Effect 4
Public Policy Transparency	.750	1.000	.752	.632
Community Involvement	.667	.830	1.000	.720
Creating Accountability	.750	.782	.835	1.000
Public Policy Innovation	1.000	.740	.667	.632

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the equation values that appear meet the assumption of *discriminant validity* and are suitable for use.

Path Coefficient Testing

As for the *path coefficient test*, it can be found through the following table:

Table 6: R Square Test

Variable	R Square
Public Policy Transparency (X)	0,883
Community Engagement (Y1)	0,863
Creating Accountability (Y2)	0,873
Public Policy Innovation (Z)	0,853

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2023

The R Square value of the variable of increasing community involvement can be explained by the variables of public policy transparency and public policy innovation of 86.3%, while the remaining 13.7% can be explained by other variables that have not been discussed in the study. The variable of creating accountability can be explained by the variables of public policy transparency and public policy innovation of 87.3%, while the remaining 12.7% can be explained by other variables that have not been discussed in the study.

Hypothesis Test

The results of hypothesis testing through the following table, namely

Table 7: Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Influence	T-Statistics	P-Value	Result
H1	Public policy transparency on community engagement	5,401	0,001	Accepted
H2	Public policy transparency towards creating accountability	6,544	0,001	Accepted
H3	Public policy transparency towards public policy innovation	4,245	0,002	Accepted
H4	Public policy innovation towards increasing community engagement	5,322	0,000	Accepted
H5	Public policy innovation towards creating accountability	6,212	0,001	Accepted
H6	Public policy transparency on community involvement through public policy innovation as an intervening variable	4,344	0,002	Accepted
H7	Public policy transparency towards creating accountability through public policy innovation as an intervening variable	3,671	0,000	Accepted

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2023

According to the table above, partially the variables of public policy transparency affect community involvement, create accountability and affect public policy innovation. The variable of public policy innovation affects community involvement and creates accountability. Simultaneously, public policy transparency affects community involvement and has the effect of creating accountability through public policy innovation variables as intervening variables.

5. DISCUSSION

Public Policy Transparency Affects the Involvement of the People of Medan City

The results of the study stated that Public Policy Transparency affect the involvement of the people of Medan City. This is in accordance with research (Robinson, 2020) which states that the transparency of public policies applied to the community must be based on increasing community involvement in providing responses and deciding policies that are appropriate for the community.

Public Policy Transparency Has an Effect on Creating Accountability

According to the results of the existing research Public Policy Transparency has an effect on creating accountability. This is in accordance with research (Moon, Suerie, 2022) which states that a policy is transparent in the public, it will make policymakers have to create accountability for the policy for the community

Public Policy Transparency Affects Public Policy Innovation

According to the results of the existing research Public Policy Transparency affect public policy innovation. This is in accordance with research (Dzakaklo, Theophilus Kodzo, Hlovor, Ishmael Kwabla and Dah, 2023) which states that public policy transparency must be interspersed with alternative policies that are part of public policy innovation so that the policies decided can satisfy the public

Public Policy Innovation Affects the Involvement of the People of Medan City

According to the results of existing research, the variables of public policy innovation affect the involvement of the people of Medan City. This is in line with research (Carlsson, Vanja and Rönnblom, 2022) which states that existing public policy innovations can be easily carried out through the comprehensive use of community involvement

Public Policy Innovation Has an Effect on Creating Accountability

The results of the study stated that public policy innovation had an effect on the involvement of the people of Medan City. This is in accordance with research (Hout, Wil, Wagner & Demena, 2022) who explained that the more able to create innovation in deciding policies that will be implemented by the community, it will create accountability so that the policy can be properly informed.

Public Policy Transparency Affects Community Involvement in Medan City through Public Policy Innovation as an Intervening Variable

The results of the study explain that the variable Public Policy Transparency affect the involvement of the people of Medan City through public policy innovation as an intervening variable. This is in accordance with research (Steudt, Wolf Robin, Medranda Morales, Narcisa and Sánchez Montoya, 2020) which explains that the more transparent the policies produced, the more innovative the decisions will be decided through the involvement of the community in incorporating ideas and suggestions into the policies that are to be taken.

Public Policy Transparency Affects Creating Accountability through Public Policy Innovation as an Intervening Variable

The results of the study explain that the variable Public Policy Transparency It has an effect on creating accountability through public policy innovation as an intervening

variable. This is in accordance with research (Yanuardi, Vijge, Marjanneke J. and Biermann, 2021) which states that the more innovative the policy design that is to be decided, it will have an impact on the transparency and accountability of information that can be accessed by the public at any time.

Implementation

The more transparent public policies are accompanied by community involvement and creating accountability to be open, it will have an impact on the process of creating innovations in public policies intended to create policies that are in favor of the community.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, the variable of public policy transparency partially affects community involvement, creates accountability and affects public policy innovation. The variable of public policy innovation affects community involvement and creates accountability. Simultaneously, public policy transparency affects community involvement and has the effect of creating accountability through public policy innovation variables as intervening variables.

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